

DESIGN AND FATIGUE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE TURBINE BLADES UNDER OCEAN WAVE CURRENT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

In this present study, the design, analysis and life prediction of a composite ocean current turbine (OCT) blade have been investigated. Unlike wind turbines, load determination in current turbines is far more complex due to higher fluid density, buoyant forces, added mass, and randomness of ocean waves, tides and currents. As a result of this complexity, an accurate method for obtaining blade loading is necessary. Traditionally, the wind industry uses the NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory) codes, based on BEMT (Blade Element Momentum Theory) for design and analysis. Modifications have been made to these codes in order to account for oceanic conditions. A procedure was developed that took into account the inclusion of a core inside the blade. A study was performed on the corresponding change in mode shape, flap and edgewise stiffness, and mass density. The modelling of an OCT blade containing a foam core was completed in SolidWorks. The static analysis revealed that high stress arises inside the foam. Furthermore, ocean current data from the Gulf Stream was collected and analysed to carry out a fatigue analysis. Utilizing the S-N diagram of the core material and Palmgren-Miner's rule, blade fatigue life was estimated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Unlike wind turbines, marine hydrokinetic devices undergo high density fluid interactions and randomness in ocean waves, tides and currents [1]. As such, resource characterization and load determination are far more complex than those of wind turbines. For example, with the case of an OCT, one has to consider acceleration of the fluid displaced by blade rotation, added mass effect, buoyancy effect, velocity shear, randomness in ocean current velocity, and wind driven effects in the ocean. Attempts have been made to determine these loadings using the NREL codes based on BEMT [2] – which is developed by the coupling of momentum loss and blade element theory. Modifications have been made for water and buoyancy effects in the NREL codes. Although such modifications allow first hand load calculations, substantial improvement is necessary to reflect the entire loading spectrum. The other difficulty that arises in the prediction of fatigue life, is the randomness in loading which is inherent in ocean currents and waves [3, 4]. In an effort to address these issues, a comprehensive loading and fatigue analysis was performed devoted to two areas, namely, i) conversion of wave forces into loading on submerged turbine blades, ii) estimation of random loading due to ocean current. Finite element codes were developed to generate S-N diagrams using failure theories for blades made from composite and sandwich constructions. Palmgren-Miner's rule was used in conjunction with the S-N diagram and loading spectrum to make a prediction on fatigue life. Blade design, load calculations and procedures for life prediction will be presented.

2 BLADE DESIGN

Geometric specifications and design of a composite ocean current turbine blade are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1, respectively. The blade is a sandwich construction of carbon/epoxy composite with

syntactic foam as a core material. The composite skin provides enhanced corrosion resistance to marine water, a high specific modulus, and hydrodynamic formability. Syntactic foam is added to prevent the composite shell from buckling and to bring the blade close to neutral buoyancy, resulting in decreased load fluctuation. Unidirectional AS4/3501-6 was used for the carbon/epoxy composite [5], with a stacking sequence of $[-45/-45/0_4/-45/45]$. SF46 micro-balloons were used in the syntactic foam [6]. These material properties are shown in Table 2.

Blade modelling was performed by importing 25 FX77 Wortmann airfoils into SolidWorks as 3D curves. Each cross-sectional area was scaled to chord length, rotated to twist angle, and positioned appropriately. They were then lofted together and shelled, creating a 4.088 mm skin. The combined mass of the skin and foam is 4.67 kg. If the same blade was composed of 1060 Aluminum alloy, it would weigh 15.44 kg, an increase of over 230%. Using high quality composite materials, results in a lightweight yet durable design. Next, the hollow blade was filled and exported to ANSYS for analysis. Before being able to run a simulation, blade loading must be calculated. This was carried out using the NREL codes, PreComp, BModes, and FAST.

Figure 1: Ocean current turbine blade.

Table 1: Geometric specifications of the blade

Length	1.22 m
Maximum Chord (at root)	311 mm
Minimum Chord (at tip)	112 mm
Maximum height of chord	74 mm
Minimum height of chord	13 mm
Hydrofoil Cross-Section	FX77 Wortmann

Table 2: Material properties of a composite and syntactic foam

	Density ρ (kg/m^3)	Longitudinal Modulus, E_1 (GPa)	Transverse in Plane Modulus, E_2 (GPa)	Transverse out of Plane Modulus, E_3 (GPa)	In Plane Shear Modulus, G_{12} (GPa)	Out of Plane shear Modulus, G_{23} (GPa)	Out of Plane shear Modulus, G_{13} (GPa)	Major in Plane Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	Out of Plane Poisson's ratio, ν_{23}	Out of Plane Poisson's ratio, ν_{13}	Lay up Sequences	Thicknes s of layer
Carbon/ Epoxy	1600	147	10.3	10.3	7	3.7	7	0.27	0.54	0.27	$[(+45)_2 0_2]_s$	0.511 mm
Syntactic Foam	450	2.5	-	-	0.96	-	-	0.3	-	-	-	-

3 LOAD CALCULATION USING MODIFIED NREL CODES

Loading on the ocean current turbine blade were determined by means of a new approach, using NREL codes based on BEMT. Fig. 2 shows a flow chart of the load calculation. Since the NREL codes are designed for hollow turbine blades, several modifications were necessary for foam inclusion. Section properties, such as flap-wise stiffness, edge-wise stiffness, torsion stiffness, and mass density of the core were taken into consideration. Using AutoCAD, each airfoil was offset inwards 4.088 mm in order to create the 2D core geometry. AutoCAD then calculated the area and moments of inertia about the quarter chord. The area was multiplied by the foam density to give the mass density per section. The moments of inertia were multiplied by the core modulus of elasticity in order to generate the foam flap and edgewise stiffness. Finally, all of these values were added to the 25 sections in the original PreComp output file.

BModes reads the revised PreComp output file and calculates the blade mode shape and eigenvalues. The mode shapes are fitted by the 6th order normalized polynomial functions, which are included in FAST.

Since ocean current turbines are surrounded by water, a much higher density fluid in comparison to air, added mass needs to be taken into consideration. Additionally, the force of buoyancy cannot be overlooked in our calculations. We can account for added mass and buoyancy by adjusting the gravitational constant in FAST. Multiplying the cross-sectional area of the 25 blade sections by the density of water results in the section buoyancy. Multiplying the mass of the displaced water by 0.5 added mass coefficient, results in the added mass for each section. Subtracting the buoyancy from the mass of the skin and core, results in the net blade gravity. The average ratio of net blade gravity to total mass is multiplied by the gravitational constant, resulting in the adjusted gravity for the blade. These values are shown in Table 3.

Figure 2: A flow chart of load calculation

Table 3: Net gravities of each cross section

Section Station	Mass of Skin and Core (kg/m)	Added Mass (kg/m)	Total Mass (kg/m)	Buoyancy (kg/m)	Net Blade Gravity (kg/m)	Net Blade Gravity to Total Mass
1	9.57	7.32	16.88	14.63518	-5.07	-0.3002
2	9.43	7.19	16.62	14.37635	-4.95	-0.29759
3	9.15	6.92	16.07	13.84104	-4.69	-0.29173
4	8.73	6.52	15.25	13.0355	-4.30	-0.28217
5	8.19	6.00	14.19	12.00535	-3.82	-0.26884
6	7.56	5.41	12.97	10.81893	-3.26	-0.25138
7	6.87	4.77	11.65	9.546573	-2.67	-0.22936
8	6.18	4.13	10.31	8.267455	-2.09	-0.20297
9	5.49	3.52	9.00	7.033161	-1.55	-0.17164
10	4.84	2.95	7.79	5.892561	-1.05	-0.13512
11	4.25	2.44	6.68	4.872871	-0.63	-0.0938
12	3.72	1.99	5.71	3.986389	-0.27	-0.04751
13	3.26	1.62	4.87	3.236776	0.02	0.004029
14	2.91	1.36	4.27	2.7261	0.19	0.043453
15	2.62	1.15	3.77	2.300828	0.32	0.084393
16	2.37	0.98	3.36	1.965971	0.41	0.12134
17	2.17	0.85	3.02	1.693526	0.48	0.158194
18	2.01	0.74	2.75	1.478819	0.53	0.192787
19	1.88	0.66	2.54	1.311867	0.57	0.224129
20	1.78	0.59	2.37	1.174732	0.60	0.255266
21	1.70	0.54	2.24	1.079981	0.62	0.277789
22	1.65	0.51	2.15	1.010906	0.64	0.295727
23	1.61	0.49	2.10	0.975421	0.64	0.303532
24	1.59	0.48	2.07	0.952984	0.64	0.308693
25	1.58	0.47	2.05	0.94177	0.64	0.311172
Average						0.000328
Gravitational Constant						9.81
Adjusted Gravity						0.003222

With all data, including the section modulus, mode shapes, and lift and drag coefficients, loaded into FAST’s AeroDyne module, the loading on each blade section was calculated. Loadings were derived using a rotation of 50 rpm at 20 different constant current velocities ranging from 0.4 to 2.7 m/s. The most frequent velocity in the Fort Lauderdale, Gulf Stream is 1.5 m/s. The steady state [7] stall model was used with a simulation time of 6 seconds. Fig. 3 shows a distribution of normal and tangential load on the blade at 1.5 m/s.

Figure 3: Load distribution on the blade (Bin 10 at 1.5 m/s)

4 MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND STATIC ANALYSIS

To find the stress distribution of the blade, a static analysis was performed by applying calculated normal and tangential loads to the finite element blade model. The static structural module of ANSYS Workbench 15.0 was used for the analysis. Fig. 4 shows a schematic of the finite element model, where both composite shell and solid foam were modelled using solid elements. Material properties in Table 2 were used in the analysis. The blade root was constrained and normal and tangential forces were applied to the nodes located at the intersection points of the pitch axis and foil. Fig.5 shows a stress distribution of the foam.

Figure 4: Finite element model of ocean current turbine blade

Figure 5: Stress distribution of the foam (von-Mises stress)

5 OCEAN CURRENT AND FATIGUE ANALYSIS

Next, the Fort Lauderdale Gulf Stream data was organized into a form suitable for fatigue analysis. Fig. 6 shows the current velocity histogram at 47.5 m depth. These data were recorded from May/25/2013 to April/28/2014 with a sampling period of 15 minutes. The number of occurrences were calculated by dividing the data into 20 bins, shown in Fig. 6. The fatigue analysis was carried out as follows. First, the corresponding load of each bin was calculated using the modified NREL codes. Second, a stress analyses was performed using the load, and the highest stress from the foam was calculated. Third, the fatigue life from the corresponding stress was found using the syntactic foam S-N diagram [8]. Finally, by repeating the above calculation for all velocity bins, and using the number

of occurrences in the histogram, the cumulative damage was calculated. Palmgren-Miner's rule, shown in Eq. (1), was used to determine cumulative damage, D .

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^k D_i = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{N_i} \quad (1)$$

Where, k is a number of bins, D_i is the cumulative damage of the i th bin, n_i is the fatigue cycle of the i th bin, and N_i is the fatigue life of i th loading condition.

Figure 6: Current velocity histogram

Results specify that the blade core will undergo 0.0034 damage (D) annually. This indicates that the core material chosen is ideal for OCT application. Being able to withstand the oscillating flow rate in the Florida Gulf Stream is essential to reliable and long term turbine deployment. Utilizing composite materials has resulted in a lightweight, yet durable and practical design.

7 SUMMARY

Static and fatigue analyses of an ocean current turbine were performed using the NREL codes, based on blade element momentum theory. A new approach was applied to these codes in order to consider the section properties of the core and the effect of added mass. AutoCAD was utilized to calculate the section properties of the foam and those values were added to the input file computed by PreComp. The added mass was calculated by computing the area of each airfoil and multiplying by the added mass coefficient. Blade net gravity was also obtained at each section, in order to calculate the adjusted gravitational coefficient for FAST. This new approach enabled us to perform a dynamic analysis of the blade filled with foam using the conventional NREL codes. Furthermore, the calculated loading was applied to the finite element blade model to obtain the stress distribution and fatigue life of the blade. The static analysis revealed that high stress arises inside the foam, resulting in fatigue failure. Fatigue analysis was performed using collected ocean current data from the Fort Lauderdale, Florida Gulf Stream in conjunction with the foam S-N diagram and Palmgren-Miner's rule. Results indicate that materials chosen are ideal for OCT application in the Florida Gulf stream.

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